

Innovative Preservation methods applied to seafood products

Abubakar Shuaibu

Abstract

Fish and other seafood products are important dietary components that are consumed all around the world. However, seafood products are highly perishable and thus require proper processing to maintain their quality and safety this has led to the development of a wide range of processing, preservation, and analytical technique. The present article reviews innovative processing technologies applied for the preservation and shelf life extension of seafood products. These primarily include: high hydrostatic pressure, natural preservatives, ozonation, irradiation, pulse light technology and retort pouch processing, Non-Thermal Atmospheric Plasma (NTAP); Pulsed Electric Fields (PEF); Pulsed Light (PL); Ultrasound (US); Electrolysed Water (EW).

Keywords : seafood spoilage; food safety; high hydrostatic pressure; natural preservatives; ozonation; irradiation; pulse light technology; retort pouch processing; Non-Thermal Atmospheric Plasma (NTAP); Pulsed Electric Fields (PEF); Pulsed Light (PL); Ultrasound (US); Electrolysed Water (EW)

1. Introduction

The word “seafood” includes free-swimming, pelagic and freshwater fish, crustaceans, mollusks and the respective aqua cultured species. The most important crustaceans include: crabs, lobsters, crayfish, shrimp and prawns, while the most important mollusks include: mussels, scallops, cockles, oysters, clams, squid and octopus. Fish may be further categorized as saltwater, freshwater fish, fatty and non-fatty fish and free-swimming aqua cultured fish. Although the structure and composition of fish are similar to those of meat, the former bear distinctive features. Firstly, fish have no obvious deposit of fat. Even though the fat content of fish may exceed 25% w/w, it is mostly dispersed within muscle fibers. A second feature is that the connective tissue is usually less than 3% as opposed to meat in which the connective tissue content may be as high as 15%. A third specific feature of fish muscle is the presence of non-protein nitrogenous compounds composed of free amino acids, volatile nitrogen bases such as ammonia, trimethylamine and trimethylamine oxide (TMAO), creatine, taurine, uric acid, anserine, carnosine and histamine. The composition of fish muscle varies significantly with species, size, fishing grounds and diet, especially in the case of aqua cultured fish (Doyle et al., 2001).

The typical composition for a non-fatty fish such as cod would be: moisture 81.5%, protein 16.5%, fat 0.4%, carbohydrate 0%, ash 1.2%. The respective composition for a fatty fish such as salmon would be: moisture 63.5%, protein 17.5%, fat 16.5%, carbohydrate 0%, and ash 1%. Fish

flesh can also contain non-protein nitrogenous compounds, typical examples being those of cod (total N = 2.83%, protein N = 2.47%) and lobster (total N = 2.72%, protein N = 2.04%). The proximate composition of selected seafood products is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Proximate % composition of selected seafood products (Watt and Merrill et al., 1996)

Seafood	Moisture	Carbohydrates	Proteins	Fat	Ash
Bony fish					
Swordfish	75.8	0	19.2	4.0	1.3
Salmon	63.4	0	17.4	16.5	1.0
Mackerel	68.1	0	18.7	12.0	1.2
Crustaceans					
Shrimp	72.5	0.9	20.5	5.5	0.8
Lobster	79.2	0.5	16.2	1.9	2.2
Crab	80.0	0.6	16.1	1.6	1.7
Mollusks					
Oysters	80.5	5.6	9.8	2.1	2.0
Scallops	80.3	3.4	14.8	14.8	1.4
Squid/mantle	83.5	1.4	13.5	0.8	0.7

Source: (Watt, B.K.; Merrill, A.L. *Composition of Foods: Raw, Processed, Prepared. Agriculture Handbook No. 8*; U.S. Department of Agriculture)

2. Seafood spoilage

In general, the rapid spoilage of fish after harvest is mainly due to different mechanisms, including (i) post mortem enzymatic autolysis, (ii) microbial spoilage and (iii) oxidation of lipids. Immediately after slaughter, the endogenous autolytic enzymes present in fish muscle become highly active and begin a proteolytic process which leads to protein decomposition and solubilization; peptides and free amino acids formed via autolysis, as well as biogenic amines formed through the action of decarboxylases, lead to fish spoilage. Trimethylamine (TMA) is the main indicator of unpleasant 'fishy smell'; it is a volatile nitrogenous base, produced post mortem in fish by the degradation of Trimethylamine Oxide (TMAO). TMA is below the detection limit in freshly caught fish, but some bacteria, such as *Shewanella putrefaciens*, *Aeromonas* spp., Enterobacteriaceae, *Photobacterium phosphoreum*, *Vibrio* spp., *Micrococcus*, *Acinetobacter*, *Moraxella*, use TMAO as an osmo-regulation to avoid dehydration in marine environments and tissue waterlogging in fresh water by reducing TMAO to TMA, creating the ammonia-like off-flavours other biological amines (BAs) are produced through microbial decarboxylation, including histamine, putrescine, cadaverine, spermidine and spermine. Among BAs, histamine is the degradation product of histidine. Some histamine is produced by endogenous tissue enzymes in relatively small quantities, immediately after fish capture, while most histamine is produced by the bacterial flora. The bacteria directly involved in the production of high levels of histamine are those possessing the enzyme histidine decarboxylase, such as *P. phosphoreum*, Enterobacteriaceae and Pseudomonadaceae (including *Morganella morganii* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Proteus* and *Pseudomonas* spp.)

However, it is known that changes in the organoleptic characteristics of fish depend mainly on an increase in the microbial load. In particular, two groups of microorganisms can be distinguished in fish, namely, the indigenous or autochthonous microbiota and the exogenous or allochthonous microbiota. In fish from temperate or warm waters, the autochthonous microbial flora consists mainly of narrow aerobic or facultative aerobic mesophilic Gram-negative (*Pseudomonas* spp., *Moraxella*, *Acinetobacter*, *Flavobacterium*, *Xanthomonas* and *Vibrio*) and Gram-positive bacterial species (*Bacillus*, *Corynebacterium*, *Micrococcus* and *Lactobacillus*). Whereas, in cold-water fish, microbiota consists of Gram-negative species in the surface mucus (mainly *Pseudomonas*, *Alteromonas*, *Photobacterium*, and *Shewanella*) and Gram-positive species in the intestinal contents (*Clostridium* spp.) (Novoslavskij et al., 2015). The exogenous microbiota consists of typically terrestrial microbial species, such as *Enterococcus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, *Enterobacter*, *Klebsiella*, *Shigella* and *Yersinia*. This type of contamination mainly affects fish living near the coast contaminated by sewage from large urban agglomerations (Klase et al., 2019).

Finally, particularly in fatty fish, chemical oxidation of lipids is a common cause of spoilage which leads to the formation of all those compounds conferring the characteristic rancid off-flavors to spoiled fatty fish. Spoilage can be also caused by lipid hydrolysis through lipolysis. Lipolytic enzymes can either be endogenous of the fish itself (present in the fish skin, blood and tissue) or can be the product of the psychrotrophic microorganism's metabolism. Regardless the origin of the enzymes, the fatty acids formed during hydrolysis interact with sarcoplasmic and myofibrillar fish proteins, causing denaturation and texture changes (Huis in 't Veld et al., 1996).

Even though the spoilage causes of fish can be explained through the above-mentioned processes, in general, all these mechanisms progress simultaneously, accelerating the overall spoilage of these products.

3. Innovative Preservation Methods Applied to seafood Products

The purpose of an optimal preservation method should be counteracting the causes of food deterioration maintaining its chemical (its composition), physical (its condition), organoleptic (taste, smell and color) and nutritional (presence of proteins, fats and carbohydrates, vitamins, mineral salts and water) properties.

Therefore, besides traditional preservation methods, the great challenge of modern food technology is to develop less aggressive preservation processes, which keep the product 'natural', although with a lower shelf-life.

Natural preservatives, high hydrostatic pressure, Ozonation, Irradiation, retort pouch processing (RPP), non-thermal technologies are able to significantly inactivate microorganisms in food, extend shelf-life without significant changes in sensory perception and maintain the nutritional value of the processed food (Pereira et al., 2010). Among the main non-thermal inactivation techniques studied to be applied for fish products, non-thermal atmospheric plasma (NTAP), pulsed electric fields (PEF), pulsed light (PL), ultrasound (US) and electrolysed water (EW) are described in the following sections, the benefits and the limits of each method are highlighted and the potential positive or negative effect on the quality of the treated products is underlined.

3.1.1 Use of Natural Preservatives

Fresh seafood products are extremely perishable even when refrigerated and susceptible to microbial growth, autolytic activity and lipid oxidation. In order to maintain quality and extend seafood shelf life, preservatives may be added during product processing and storage. As a response to consumer demand for fresh, minimally processed foods containing no chemical additives, the food industry has turned to natural preservatives in order to maintain the quality and safety of consumed foods. Natural preservatives should be effective against a broad spectrum of bacteria and fungi, be active at low concentrations, be nontoxic, should not affect food sensory properties, should impart no flavor or color to food and, finally, should be cost-effective. Natural preservatives may be isolated from microorganisms, animals and plants (Mei

et al., 2004). The main categories of natural preservatives used in seafood products include: organic acids, essential oils and plant/algal extracts, bacteriocins and chitosan.

3.1.2 High Hydrostatic Pressure

High hydrostatic pressure (HHP) is a non-thermal method of preserving food, in which the product is processed under very high pressure, leading to the inactivation of microorganisms and enzymes in the food (Abdu et al., 2018).

Figure1. Shows Schematic diagram of high hydrostatic pressure (HHP) processing

The first food products preserved by pressure entered the Japanese market in 1990 (Rastogi et al., 2007). HHP has a similar effect on microorganisms and enzymes to high-temperature treatment.

Pressures applied during treatment are usually in the range of 100–600 MPa but may be as high as 1200 MPa for spore inactivation (sterilization). Microorganism inactivation is the result of cellular damage and biochemical changes resulting from food exposure to high pressures. It has been shown that fungi are more susceptible to damage by HHP, followed by Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria. Exposure to high pressure can also result in texture alteration of food products but such changes are reported to be reversible in the range of 100–300 MPa. Fish flesh is susceptible to thermal processing, affecting its textural and sensory properties. For this reason, HHP may be a suitable alternative to thermal processing of fish. Rastogi et al. [124] reviewed some important findings on the application of HHP to fish and shellfish products. Color changes and rancidity are side effects of exposing fish to high pressure. HP cold pasteurization or HP-

assisted pasteurization results in lower levels of protein denaturation and enhanced organoleptic properties compared to conventional fish preservation methods.

3.1.3 *Ozonation of Seafood*

The sanitizing properties of ozone (O₃) were firstly observed in 1909, in a meat storage plant in Germany, when it was observed that meat placed in proximity to an ozone generator, used to ventilate the storage container, exhibited reduced microbial load (Rollex et al.,). Since then, ozone has been used to reduce the microbial load and prevent spoilage of foods including seafood (Goche et al., 1999). It has been demonstrated that ozone treatment can effectively inhibit the spoilage of fish during cold storage. The effect of aqueous O₃ on the shelf life of VP, cold-stored rainbow trout has been investigated by (Nerantzaki et al., 2005). Ozonation treatment (for 60 or 90 min) reduced the bacterial load of fish as well as TVB-N and TMA-N compared to the control during storage.

3.1.4 *Irradiation of Seafood*

Ionizing irradiation is used as a food preservation method by the seafood industry to; extend product shelf life (by effectively destroying spoilage microorganisms), improve food safety (by destroying pathogens responsible for foodborne illnesses), delay or eliminate sprouting or ripening and control insects and invasive pests. Irradiation is achieved using gamma rays, electron beams or X-rays. The supplied energy abstracts electrons (ionizes) from atoms in the targeted food. Independent research carried out by the World Health Organization and food regulatory agencies in the USA and EU has confirmed that irradiation is safe (FDA. Center for Food Safety and Applied Nutrition 2018)

3.1.5 *Pulsed Light (PL)*

Pulsed light (PL) is a non-thermal technology, approved by the FDA (Food and Drug Administration), which involves the emission of short flashes of light in a broad spectrum (Dunn et al., 1995). PL technology was first used in the medical field to sterilize medical devices and then in water purification processes; recently, it has also found new applications in air sanitation. In 1996, the FDA approved the use of PL technology for food production, processing and handling processes (Food and Drug Administration Code of Federal Regulations). It is recommended to use the xenon lamp with surface emission of wavelengths between 200 and 1100 nm, with a cumulative treatment not exceeding 12 J/cm² and a pulse width not exceeding 2ms. In the food industry, pulsed light technology is mainly used for ready-to-eat products, meat and fish products, or dairy products, which are subject to rapid spoilage and require delicate preservation measures. The decontamination effect of PL treatments is mainly due to the photochemical changes caused by UV-C radiation on microbial DNA, in combination with the photo thermal and photo physical damage caused to cells by water vaporization and membrane destruction (Mandal et al., 2020). The effectiveness of this method has been recognized against Gram-positive and -negative bacteria, as well as fungal spores, and the lethal effect is greater

than UV treatment applied in continuous. In particular, it has been shown that Gram-positive bacteria are more resistant than Gram-negative bacteria and fungal spores show higher resistance than bacteria (Anderson et al., 2000) although (Gómez-López et al., 2005) reported opposite results. However, each microorganism has a different sensitivity to treatment and this may be related to differences in the composition of the bacterial cell wall and their protective and repair mechanisms against damage. The potential of pulsed light treatment depends on many factors, such as the exposure time, variations in the power of the UV source (which affects the electromagnetic wavelength), the presence of particles that can protect microorganisms from UV and the ability of the microorganisms to resist the radiation during exposure. High power, long treatment time and the closer distance between target and flash lamp cause an increase in microbial reduction but a consequent loss of quality, so it is necessary to find the optimal treatment conditions to improve microbiological safety without affecting food quality (Lasagabaster et al., 2005).

3.1.6 Retort Pouch Processing (RPP)

Sterilization using heat is one of the most efficient methods of food preservation. The main objective of thermal sterilization is to kill all viable microorganisms including spores present in the food in order to achieve long-term shelf stability without the need for refrigeration. The application, however, of such severe heat treatments adversely affects the nutritional value of food including losses in vitamins and essential fatty acids and protein denaturation, particularly for products processed in metal or glass containers. Optimization of thermal processing conditions for minimizing nutrient loss without compromising the quality and safety of foods is a major issue for the food industry (Simpson et al., 2004) developed and optimized a mathematical model for thermal processing of conduction-heated foods in retort able pouches. The model was validated utilizing jack mackerel. The prediction errors obtained in the validation study were under 5%. Non-significant differences were found between the experimental and predicted values. Simulations showed that a significant reduction in process time (20–30%) could be attained utilizing variable retort temperature profiles while maintaining product quality.

3.1.7 Non-Thermal Atmospheric Plasma (NTAP)

In physics and chemistry, the term plasma is used to denote the state of an ionized gas. Plasma is considered the fourth state of matter, alongside the liquid, solid and gaseous states. While the presence of plasma on Earth is relatively rare (with the exception of lightning and the aurora borealis), in the Universe, it constitutes more than 99% of known matter; the upper layers of the Earth's atmosphere (ionosphere), the outer gaseous layers of the Sun and stars and interstellar space are plasmas (natural plasmas).

Plasma can be generated artificially by supplying a gas with sufficiently high energy by means of lasers, shock waves, electric arcs, or electric and magnetic fields (glow discharge). There are two

types of plasma, thermal and non-thermal atmospheric plasma (NTAP), depending on the conditions under which it is generated. Plasma generated at ambient pressure and temperature is called cold plasma (CP), atmospheric cold plasma (ACP), or non-thermal atmospheric plasma (NTAP) and it differs from thermal plasma obtained at higher powers and pressures. To generate NTAP, any type of energy (electrical, thermal, optical, radioactive and electromagnetic) can be used to ionize gases, but mainly electrical and electromagnetic fields are used.

Plasma has a neutral ionized gaseous form consisting of ions, free electrons, gas atoms and molecules, as well as UV photons depending on the process parameters and the gas used (Fukuda et al., 2019). It is created after exposure of the gas to an electric field created between two electrodes (cathode and anode), separated by a small distance of 1 cm. The gases mainly used for plasma generation, which can also influence its properties, are oxygen (O₂), nitrogen (N₂), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and noble gases, individually or in combination for optimum results. Oxygen seems to be more effective than the other gases due to its ability to cause greater oxidation of nucleic acids and amino acids (Park et al., 2015)

Plasma technology has proven to be a successful tool in both the food sector (for the decontamination of abiotic food surfaces, such as packaging materials, foods in their final packaging and various food products) and medical sector (Shaw et al., 2015). In the last decade, NTAP technology has been widely used for the preservation of various food products, such as meat and fresh agricultural products, while its use in fish and seafood is still limited (Olatunde et al., 2019).

The effectiveness of this technology obviously depends on many factors, such as voltage, frequency, treatment time, working gas composition (WGC), post-treatment/exposure time and sample surface area (Olatunde et al., 2019). The type and concentration of reactive species (RESPE) produced, such as reactive nitrogen species (RNS) and reactive oxygen species (ROS), including ozone, peroxide, singlet oxygen and different types of nitrogen oxides (N_xO_y), are mainly responsible for the inactivation of microorganisms and depend on the above parameters.

However, this technology is only able to inactivate microorganisms on the surface of solid food, due to its poor penetration capacity. When a food has high microbial loads that form multiple layers of bacteria on the surface, the upper layers of cells protect those below and the decontamination effect is unfortunately not complete. Three mechanisms of action have been observed for the inactivation of microorganisms: (1) the direct disruption of the membrane or cell wall, with leakage of cellular components; (2) oxidative damage to membranes or intracellular components, such as proteins and carbohydrates; (3) damage to cellular DNA.

NTAP technology has recently been proposed to inactivate many common pathogens in fish products (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella* Typhimurium and Enteritidis, *Clostridium perfringens*, *E. coli*), various spoilage and spoilage microorganisms (*Pseudomonas*, hydrogen sulphide-producing microorganisms, Enterobacteriaceae), including

yeasts and fungi (*Cladosporium cladosporioides* and *Penicillium citrinum*), standing up as a precious additional tool for the successfully decontamination of various food and seafood products.

3.1.8 Pulsed Electric Fields (PEF)

PEF is an emerging technology that involves the delivery of short high-power electrical pulses (microsecond) to a product placed in a treatment chamber, confined between electrodes. The process produces modest thermal increases without causing any effect in the product. The application of an external electric field to biological cells (animal, plant or microbial) causes damage to the cell membrane. To date, a number of theoretical models have been suggested, but there is still no clear evidence of the mechanism of action at the cellular level. The most accepted theory is the electromechanical model introduced by (Zimmermann et al., 1974) which considers the cell membrane to be a capacitor with a low dielectric constant. Free charges of opposite polarity are present on both sides of a membrane (inner and outer), resulting in a natural transmembrane potential. Exposure to an electric field induces accumulation of charges inside and outside the cell across the membrane and thus an increase in transmembrane potential.

Although the technique was known 50 years ago, PEF can be still considered an emerging technology, because its industrial applications are recent. Initially, the use of PEF in food processing has attracted great interest especially as a method to improve the extraction of specific components or improve drying efficiency (Adeomowaye et al., 2001). The technology is, in fact, well suited for the extraction of high-value compounds from fish by-products, as it destroys only the biological cells in the food matrix with high extraction efficiency, also compared to other methods (He et al., 2014). Surprising results were recovered by using PEF to extract proteins from mussels, calcium and chondroitin sulphated from fish bones and proteins from abalone viscera (Li et al., 2015).

However, more recently, the use of PEF has been suggested also as a novel preservation method, due to its capacity to rapidly inactivate microorganisms, producing foods with great nutritional and sensory quality (Horita et al., 2018). It has been also shown that using PEF in combination with other non-thermal technologies such as UV irradiation, microwaves, high-intensity light pulses (HILP) and high hydrostatic pressure (HHP) increased microbial inactivation (Stoica et al., 2013).

3.1.9 Ultrasound (US)

Ultrasound is one of the innovative non-thermal techniques that is proving to be very successful in the food sector where it is actually used for freezing, cutting, drying, homogenization, degassing, foaming, filtration and extraction processes. More recently, it has been also proposed as an alternative to heat treatments to control microbial growth. Ultrasonic waves used in the food industry are low energy, high frequency (16–100 kHz) waves. Any type of system used for US production consists of three parts: (1) a current generator that supplies electricity at the

desired frequency to the transducer; (2) a transducer or converter, which converts electrical energy into mechanical vibrations (pressure waves) that are conveyed into a probe; (3) a probe that amplifies the vibration produced forming the sonication site that can be continuous or discontinuous. Typical ultrasonic systems are the ultrasonic bath, ultrasonic probes, parallel vibrating plates and radial vibrating systems. The mechanism behind sonication is the well-known phenomenon of cavitation, i.e., the repeated creation of microbubbles inside a liquid, followed by their implosion. The pressure resulting from these implosions causes the main bactericidal effect of ultrasound, which consists of a thinning of cell membranes, localized heating and production of free radicals. The effectiveness of the treatment depends on several factors, such as type of microorganism treated, amplitude of the ultrasonic waves, exposure/contact time, volume and composition of the food to be treated and temperature of the treatment. The literature reports that Gram-positive cells are more resistant to ultrasound than Gram-negative cells and this may be due to the structure of the cell wall. In addition, vegetative cells are more susceptible to bacterial spores. To make the action of ultrasound on microorganisms more effective, sonication is often combined with other treatments. It is common to use mild heat treatments (thermo-sonics), high pressures (mano-sonics), or both (mano-thermo-sonics) (Adekunte et al., 2010).

3.2.0 *Electrolysed Water (EW)*

Among the relatively new proposals, electrolytic water (EW) is attracting interest as a non-thermal technique in the food industry and agriculture. Similar to all the innovative methods mentioned above, EW is safer and more effective than traditional chemical agents, to which microorganisms are becoming increasingly resistant. In fact, it is considered as a new non-thermal and environmentally friendly sanitizer.

The antimicrobial activity of EW has been widely demonstrated against various food-borne microorganisms, such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli* O157:H7, *S. Typhimurium*, *L. monocytogenes*¹, *Campylobacter jejuni* and *V. parahaemolyticus*. It is also effective against spores, fungi and viruses present in food, environment and food processing plants. The antimicrobial activity and mechanism of action of EW against bacteria are not yet fully described. However, it is known that chlorine and reactive oxygen can break down the microbial cell membrane and cause oxidative DNA damage.

EW has various applications in the food industry; one of the most significant is in the seafood industry, although limited effectiveness in decreasing the bacterial load on seafood at room temperature has been demonstrated. The treatment of fish products with various types of EW highlights great results for microbiological quality, but also good results in inhibiting pH changes, formation of total volatile basic nitrogen (TVB-N) and activity of the enzyme polyphenol oxidase (PPO)

4. Discussion and conclusion

This article has given comprehensive information about innovative preservation techniques and here is sample evidence that the technological advancements discussed in the sections above have improved current seafood processing and preservation methods, especially in the land-based seafood industry, which delivers excellent, high quality products with good shelf-life. Thanks to non-thermal atmospheric plasma (NTAP) as it's deactivates pathogens in most fish products. These techniques also have the advantage of being environmentally friendly and energy efficient. They are therefore aligned with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that will shape world development plans over the next decade and are of great interest to Industry 4.0. Non-thermal technologies, the use of PEF treatment and ultrasound technology to improve the quality and shelf-life of seafood products has advantages (e.g., optimal control of the microbial population) and limitations (e.g., sensory changes); they are nonetheless very promising with respect to the extraction and purification of bioactive compounds from fishery discards (i.e., non-target species that are returned to the sea) and/or industrial seafood waste (i.e., skin, head, shells, backbones, etc.). hydrostatic pressure, irradiation, ozonation technique have also proven to be effective in the preservation of seafood products.

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